

STUDIES OF RELIGIOSITY AMONGST GREEK ORTHODOX YOUTH IN AUSTRALIA

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Abstract

This report summarises findings from research that was conducted on ethnic background and religiosity amongst Greek Orthodox youth. A complete bibliography is attached.

Keywords

Religiosity, Greek Orthodox, youth, Australia

I. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this report is to bring together findings from previous research that was conducted on ethnic background and religiosity amongst Greek Orthodox youth. The research commenced just over 35 years ago and findings were reported in diverse sources over the period 1984-2012. For the purposes of this report, only the key results are outlined. A complete bibliography is attached.

Given that the Orthodox Church is an immigrant church in Australia, a starting point for this program of research is the link between religion and ethnic identity. For example, Isaacs¹ in her classic studies of Greek children in Sydney, gave many examples of how Greek families encouraged children to maintain and preserve their Greek customs and social norms.

Similarly, Rosenthal and Hrynevich² proposed that Greek-Australians "... have a positive value associated with 'Greekness' which may well derive from their membership of a cohesive and structured community whose institutions are central to their lives ...". In the United States, Scourby³ studied ethno-religious factors in Greek-Americans and found strong attachments to both ethnic culture as well as identification with American society.

Within this broad context, a number of studies were conducted that examined ethnic background and religiosity amongst Greek Orthodox youth in Australia. The initial hypothesis was that being Greek helped to make one more religious (i.e., more Orthodox).

Ethnicity was considered in terms of the importance of Greek background or speaking Greek. Religiosity was defined in terms of religious practices, such as the extent of prayer, worship, fasting, participation in sacraments such as confession or Holy Communion. It emphasised religious knowledge as this is a relatively objective indicator.

II. RELIGIOSITY AND ETHNIC IDENTITY

The first and earliest topic of investigation had to do with the relationship between being Greek-Australian and religiousness.

Firstly, an investigation of 1,029 pupils in 25 secondary schools in the south-east, inner west and central areas of Sydney (439 males and 590 females) noted that self-rated levels of religiosity and ethnic identity were positively albeit lowly correlated.⁴

The largest correlation was between the importance of Greek origin and feelings about being Greek. A subsequent report on 400 high school pupils at two Greek Orthodox schools in Melbourne showed that self-rated religiosity was usually classed as moderate and independent of ethnic identity.⁵

III. GREEK LANGUAGE ENVIRONMENT

The Greek language is of direct relevance for Greek Orthodox religious instruction. This is influenced through (a) the extent to which Greek is used and (b) literacy in Greek.

Extent to which Greek is used

Pupils at Greek Orthodox high schools in Sydney are a select but important sample of Orthodox youth. As expected, they indicated that being of Greek background was quite important to them (87%) and something of which they were proud (83%) (p. 4).⁶

The parental demographics and socio-economic status of this group are not representative of all Greek-Australians but it was reported that 33% of parents spoke to their children more often in English or 41% both Greek and English. On the other hand, the pupils mainly spoke to their parents in English (51%) and almost all of them spoke to their brother(s) and/or sister(s) in English.

Greek literacy

In an early study, levels of reading were correlated 0.235 with interest in Modern Greek language.⁷ A later report⁸ studied 270 high school students from the full-time Greek Orthodox high schools in Sydney (average age = 12.7 years) with some 93% born in Australia. Participants completed the 42-item Greek *Diagnostic Test of Reading Ability*.⁹ The average score for the Greek-Australian sample was 15 out of 42 compared with an average of 28.1 for primary pupils in Greece. Performance was well below that of second grade pupils in Greece.

Students whose mother or father spoke Greek had higher levels of ability than those who spoke Greek and English or English alone. It was concluded that "...there was a substantial difference in ability between Greek pupils and Greek-Australians. Simple knowledge of some words was largely

missing from the language of these high school students for whom Greek had become a second language” (p. 96).

IV. RELIGIOUS PRACTICES AND KNOWLEDGE

Another aspect that was explored over this period was that of religious practices and knowledge. Results from an early report on the religious practices and knowledge of 527 high school pupils indicated that in the early 1980s, the religious knowledge of pupils in State high schools was limited.¹⁰

Religious knowledge

Religious knowledge was low in 1984 and continues at a low level. It is also highly selective.

On average students could report only seven out of the first 10 words of the Lord’s Prayer; two out of the 12 disciples of Jesus; less than one of the gospel writers; two out of the three main periods of fasting; one out of the seven Sacraments; 70% knew their name day of their patron saint; 14% knew what the Creed is; 28% knew what is Holy Communion; 8% knew what was the main theme of the book of Genesis (i.e., Creation); and only 3% knew the date of the Annunciation.

Sadly, written responses to the questions indicated major gaps in knowledge and remain indelibly in the author’s memory. This is a reflection not on the pupils but on external factors. These low levels of religiosity were recognised as less than ideal and from that time became the stimulus for the reforms in the Greek Orthodox special religious education provided in State schools.

A second study¹¹ began with the assumption that there was a low level of religious knowledge and sought to investigate its structure and level of difficulty.

In this study students completed a religious knowledge test that consisted of 25 multiple-choice questions. It was administered to students in a full-time Greek Orthodox College. The test contained 10 general questions on Greek Orthodox religion (e.g., Easter, Epiphany, Pentecost, Divine Liturgy, Annunciation, Sacraments, Chrysostom, fasting, Holy Spirit, Eucharist); 10 questions based on the Old Testament (e.g., Job, Noah, Tower of Babel, Baal, Garden of Eden, Sodom and Gomorrah, Ten Commandments, the first sin, David and Goliath, books of the Old Testament) and five questions from the New Testament (e.g., Prodigal Son, Lazarus, Good Samaritan, John the Baptist, Armageddon). No claim is made that these topics are truly representative of Orthodox religious knowledge but the items sought to assess some facts with which an Orthodox Christian might be familiar. A multiple-choice format rather than short answer test was used because it allowed for recognition of answers and it was less threatening for those students who may have less religious knowledge or experience. Students were encouraged to guess if they were not sure of an answer.

The most familiar item of religious knowledge was that of Noah and the Ark as well as knowledge of the fasting days of the week. The former may signify an item of information that

might be well known amongst the general public and the latter might represent knowledge acquired as part of the routine of the full-time Greek Orthodox College within which the study was conducted.

The most difficult items related to knowledge of the Holy Spirit as the Comforter and the patience of Job. The lack of familiarity with the Comforter is a serious lack of fundamental knowledge and indicates that few are aware of the details of Pentecost, or familiar with the New Testament and that many have not made the transition from the standard Orthodox prayer that calls upon the *Paraclete* as heavenly king and spirit of truth. This prayer is recited regularly in Greek and may also represent a linguistic deficit in knowledge. The lack of knowledge of Job emphasises that awareness of the Old Testament is lacking. It may indicate that students had not been exposed sufficiently to key examples of faith and from the Old Testament even in religious classes.

Figure 1 is a map that sets out the student performance and the question difficulties from the test on the same scale. Each X in the figure represents around three students and the left-hand side is like a chart turned sideways that shows the distribution of students across these values from least to most religious knowledge. On the right-hand side of the figure are the 25 questions. The questions are also displayed in terms of difficulty on the same scale from easiest to more difficult.

Note: Each X represents 3 students; the left-hand side of the figure represents the distribution of students; the right-hand side represents the distribution of test questions plotted according to difficulty

Figure 1. An item-ability map of Greek Orthodox religious knowledge

The placement of students and items on the same dimension allowed one to consider how well the different questions matched the students' range of knowledge. Inspection of the figure shows that it did not take much religious knowledge for full-time Greek Orthodox high school pupils to answer questions about Easter Sunday, Noah, fasting days or the Divine Liturgy. They needed an extremely high level of religious knowledge to be able to answer questions about the Comforter, the parable of the Good Samaritan, Job and Sodom and Gomorrah. Indeed, about half the items were generally above the level of the religious knowledge of this group.

The religious background of the participants was also surveyed and there was no statistically significant effect of age, gender, church attendance or prayer on the level of religious knowledge. Frequency of Holy Communion, fasting, attendance at Confession, Bible reading and Sunday School attendance were significant factors affecting the level of religious knowledge.

V. RELIGIOUS PRACTICES AND KNOWLEDGE IN GREEK ORTHODOX HIGH SCHOOLS

Another study¹² sought to document aspects of the religious background of Greek Orthodox high school pupils and secondly to see whether this influenced their interest in religion as a school subject. Thirdly, the study also examined interest in Greek Orthodoxy as a subject compared to all other subjects. Fourthly, the importance, relevance, the difficulty of the religion subject, ability in the subject, quality of teaching and homework or study time as components of interest were also examined.

The participants in the study were pupils from all three full-time Greek Orthodox Colleges in Sydney. A total of 279 pupils ranging in age from 11 to 15 years took part. The median number of years that pupils attended Greek Orthodox schools was ranged from 1-10 years.

Religious practices

As a guide to their religious practices, 30% of pupils had attended church last Sunday (In some schools church attendance is rostered); 37% said they prayed last night; 20% fasted weekly while 41% fasted three to four times a year; 6% of pupils read the Bible daily or weekly and 17% indicated that they never read the Bible; and more than 66% of these pupils had never attended Sunday School. Only a minority of pupils in these schools (7%) considered themselves very religious.

Interest in religion

Preferences for Greek Orthodoxy as a subject were ranked from 0 (highest interest of all the subjects studied) to 1 (the lowest interest in all the subjects studied). The average rank for interest in Greek Orthodoxy was 0.508 or around the middle in terms of preferences. The quality of teaching of religion was rated above average at 0.695 but correlated only .426 with interest in the subject. Interest in Greek Orthodoxy as a subject was related to perceptions of its importance ($r=.613$) and whether it was the pupils' best subject ($r=.628$).

General knowledge of religions and general knowledge

The final study in this research program was conducted in 2012.¹³ It considered the general knowledge of religions by Greek Orthodox high school pupils. The participants in this study were 93 students across Years 6, 8, 10 and 12 of a full-time Greek Orthodox College. Students completed a survey with 13 general knowledge and 13 religious knowledge questions during class time. The study was undertaken in conjunction with an anonymous survey of the mission of the school. Again, no claim is made that the sample is representative of all Greek Orthodox colleges.

The *General Knowledge Quiz* comprised 13 short answer, general knowledge questions. These sampled geography, current affairs, art, medicine, technology, science, history, literature. The questions were from the information sub-test of the former *Naylor-Harwood Adult Intelligence Scale*. Within the time frame of a school lesson and having regard for the limits of each student it was decided to use only half the 26 questions (alternate questions) so as not to overload the students. The internal consistency reliability of the 13 questions was moderate ($\alpha = .776$).

The *Religious Knowledge Quiz* comprised 13 questions. It was adapted from the online version of the The Pew Forum on Religion and Public Life¹⁴ US survey of general religious knowledge. The questions were altered to a short answer format to be consistent with the general knowledge quiz. Some questions were replaced so as to be acceptable to the participants. The content related to a number of faiths (e.g., Buddhism, Hindu, Judaism, Catholicism). The *Religious Knowledge Quiz* had a moderate internal consistency reliability ($\alpha = .757$). The proportion of correct responses to each question are described in Table 1 and the questions have been ordered by the level of agreement, viz:

Table 1.

Greek Orthodox school students' general religious knowledge (N=95)

Topic	Per cent correct ¹
Orthodox belief about bread and wine used for Communion	78%
Ramadan	59%
Religion of Pakistan	49%
Mother Teresa's religion	45%
Bible figure associated with the exodus from Egypt	28%
Theme of the Book of Genesis	21%
Vishnu and Shiva	17%
Nirvana	14%
Bible figure obedient to God despite suffering	6%
Jewish Sabbath	5%
Joseph Smith's religion	3%
Person who inspired the Protestant Reformation	2%
Talmud	0%

¹All percentages rounded

Students are most familiar with a key tenet of the Orthodox faith in relation to the Eucharist and the body and blood of Christ. Their Biblical knowledge of Old Testament persons and events is not high. Even lower is their knowledge of the details of other faiths such as Judaism, Hinduism and Buddhism.

Figure 2. *Overlap between general knowledge and religious knowledge.*

On some of these questions it is possible to compare these results with those of the Pew Survey. Of course, the comparison is not strictly valid as it compares the short answer questions in this study with multiple-choice answers in the online survey where people have the advantage of guessing; but more importantly it involves a comparison between a school sample (Year 12) and an adult sample. The Greek Orthodox students showed greater knowledge of the Eucharist. They were not as knowledgeable on most details of other faiths (Catholicism, Hinduism, Buddhism, Judaism, Mormonism, Lutheranism).

Their knowledge of the Old Testament was also greatly reduced (e.g., knowledge of Moses, Job).

A component of general religious knowledge might be attributable in part to the ability of a student to retain information. It was suggested, however, that general knowledge and general religious knowledge are largely separate domains. If it is assumed that it is valid to total the scores on the two tests then in this study only about 23% of the variance in the overall religious knowledge was attributable to general knowledge. The ways in which religious knowledge and general information are linked is also shown in the

accompanying Figure 2, which plots the proportion correct on the same dimension. There is some overlap but it is minimal. Most of the easier questions related to general information. Most of the more difficult questions were of a religious nature.

This study demonstrated that Greek Orthodox high school pupils did not have accurate knowledge of other faiths. Even a key tenet of the Orthodox faith that the bread and wine in Holy Communion are the body and blood of Jesus was known by only four-fifths of students.

Although general knowledge and religious knowledge are linked, there is evidence that religion is a specific domain. Most items of religion required a specialised knowledge that had not been obtained by this group.

VI. PERCEPTIONS OF THE RELIGIOUS MISSION OF THE ORTHODOX COLLEGE

The last research project examined students' perceptions of a school's stated mission statements. The participants in this study were the same 93 students across Years 6, 8, 10 and 12 of a full-time Greek Orthodox College.¹⁶

Only around half believed that the school convinced them that the Orthodox faith is true and just under half said that it made them feel more Greek. A notable feature of these results is a decline in feeling more Orthodox from Year 6 to Year 12.

Figure 3. Students' perception of the school's mission from Grade 6 to Grade 12.

VII. RELIGIOUS PRACTICES AND KNOWLEDGE IN SUNDAY SCHOOLS

All the groups examined to date were based in schools – either State schools or more often the full-time Greek Orthodox high schools. A different study of 254 Greek Orthodox Sunday School pupils¹⁷ provided a unique and different vantage point from which to survey religiosity.

The sample covered every senior catechetical school in metropolitan Sydney and the mean age of the group was 14.3 years. Just under one quarter (24%) rated themselves as very religious and this was not correlated with ethnic identity.

As expected, there were increased levels of participation in religious behaviours. It was reported that "...there was a high frequency of Holy communion but this varied appreciably within the sample, with most young people taking communion around 3-6 times per year.... Higher rates of confession compared with general sample... most attending only 1-2 times

per year. Fasting appeared to be a frequently occurring religious practice... there appeared to be little involvement with or study of the Bible... a high incidence of prayer, with 22.5% praying at least morning and night and 57.1% praying at least each morning or night" (p. 53).

VIII. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

What might one conclude from all this data? There is information from a variety of sources about diverse groups. Studies included students in State schools, students in full-time Greek Orthodox colleges, Sunday School students as well as groups from both Melbourne and Sydney. The various reports canvassed religious knowledge, religious practices, interest in religion, ethnic background, familiarity with Greek as well as the outcomes of schooling. The results are suggestive and some key findings are summarised below.

Identity and religiosity

Greek background (or identity) is important to young people. It is interwoven with religiousness in complex ways.

Greek language

In terms of Greek language, there is evidence that Greek literacy is limited. The fact that even students in a Greek Orthodox full-time high school had a reading level below that of Year 2 in Greece, is a major concern.

Religious knowledge

Adolescents generally, whether they attend State schools or the full-time Greek Orthodox high schools, are low in their level of religious knowledge. Students found it difficult to answer questions about basic dogma, parables or Old Testament events.

Participation in religion

Only 7% of pupils in full-time Greek Orthodox schools considered themselves very religious. This has implications for the religious ethos of the Orthodox colleges.

Students in Sunday Schools were much more religious than students in the full-time Greek colleges. They showed increased levels of participation in religious behaviours.

General knowledge of religions

This study demonstrated that Greek Orthodox high school pupils did not have accurate knowledge of other faiths. Moreover, their knowledge of Orthodoxy is varied.

For instance, in the full-time colleges, just over one fifth were not clear that the bread and wine in Holy Communion are the body and blood of Jesus. There was also evidence that religion is a specific domain of learning independent of general knowledge.

Perceptions of religious mission of the school

It was a concern that students reported that their school had not made them feel more Orthodox. This may be part of an adolescent disillusionment with schooling in general or it may indicate a specific sentiment about Greek Orthodox Colleges.

Limitations

At the outset it is important to advise the reader that the results in this report relate to group data. In a sense, the percentages are averages and there will be individual exceptions. One cannot make accurate predictions about a young person on the basis of these results; all that one can do is to make some statements of probability. Like all survey results the findings have a margin of error, that is, the percentages quoted are plus or minus some percent that can be easily determined. In addition, the samples are not representative or drawn randomly so this limits generalisation to youth in other states or to other colleges or school systems. Finally, the data are historical and there may be some improvement or possibly even some decline in the religious, language or ethnic background factors that have been assessed.

One aspect of the original 1984 study was not reported. Overt rudeness was expressed in a minority of the written responses. It was unique in the experience of the author. Moreover, a subsequent study of religious knowledge in a full-time Greek Orthodox high school encountered cheating even in the presence of the classroom teacher and two research assistants. It was so rampant that the data from this cohort had to be discarded in its entirety. The general impression is that (a) religion is a sensitive area of research and (b) students may feel threatened when they do not have religious knowledge.

Nevertheless, the results from 1984 through to 2012 are sobering for anyone with a concern for the welfare of youth. It will be left to each reader to draw their own inferences but it has been fortunate to have even this brief glimpse into Christian education amongst Greek-Australian youth.

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